

Biomass feed stocks for sustainable and smart biorefineries

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Abstract

Bio-based economy in Europe presently involves 22 million people and turns over roughly € 2.4 billion. The full realization of its huge potential, estimated at € 32.3 trillion revenues and 1 million new jobs, starts with the closed loop (circular) utilization of the major waste bioresources along with the first generation biomass, cultivated for food, medicinal, cosmetic and other needs.

Main aim of this work is to outline and discuss the origin, geographical distribution, availability, properties, etc., of biomass resources in 7 EU countries from the point of view of feasible strategies for integrated process and product design of exemplary sustainable smart biorefineries.

Biowastes can be classified as lignocelulosic (dead wood and wood chips, leaves, grass, straw, etc.); energy crops (e.g., switch grass) and industrial wooden residuals, etc.; lipid (vegetable oils, animal fats, algae oil); farm and municipal solid wastes.

In EU biowastes are not evenly distributed as location and temporal abundance. The lower microbiological and oxidation stability of biomass, as compared to its main fossil rivals, influence also the optimization of biorefinery designs. According to these and other criteria, the feasible feed stock options in 7 EU countries were analyzed and inventories had been prepared.

In continuation of this work the selected alternative feed stocks and their blends will be re-examined from the point of view of the design of chemical and biochemical technological platforms and biorefinery products.

Keywords: biorefinery, biomass, mixed feed stocks, biowastes, circular utilization, EU

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778168.